

Potentiometric, Spectral Investigation and Insecticidal Activity of 3-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone Monoxime (HMNQM) Complex of Copper

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The stability constants for copper(II)-HMNQM complexes have been determined in 75% (v/v) dioxan-water and 0.1 M NaClO₄ medium at 25°. Species distributions with respect to pH have been studied. Solid complexes with the composition ML₂ have been isolated. A sensitive spectrophotometric method is developed for the determination of copper. The insecticidal activity of 3-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone monoxime (HMNQM) has been determined with respect to the growth and metamorphosis of a mosquito, *Aedes aegypti*.

Oximes have been used extensively in analytical¹ and biological² fields. In order to understand the copper(II)-HMNQM interaction, stability constant values have been evaluated. The Cu^{II} complex has been characterised by magnetic and spectral studies. A sensitive spectrophotometric method has also been developed for the determination of copper after extraction of its HMNQM-complex into microcrystalline naphthalene.

Recently an insect ecdysis inhibitor, the naphthoquinone plumbagin has been reported from the African medicinal plant³. Keeping in view, the ecdysis disruption activity of naphthoquinone plumbagin, the bioefficacy of HMNQM was ascertained in the present study with respect to growth and metamorphosis of a mosquito, *Aedes aegypti* which is a vector of dreadful diseases.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometric study : Metal-ligand stability constants in solution have been determined pH-metrically. Protonation constant of the ligand was determined as 7.88, which shows that it behaves as a mild base. The values for the logarithm of the stepwise stability constants of the Cu-HMNQM complex are $\log K_1 = 7.70$ and $\log K_2 = 7.05$. The value of σ_{fit} (standard deviation) as 0.000. The extraordinarily good σ_{fit} provides assurance that the experimental refinement is as complete as expected. The species distribution curves for the ligand and its Cu^{II} complex system based on fitted equilibrium constants (figures not shown) reveal that CuL₂ is the predominant species at pH ≥ 6.72 .

Spectral study : Infrared spectral data reveal that the ligand coordinates through oxygen of the phenolic group and nitrogen of the oxime group. A medium intensity ligand band at $\sim 1280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-O) shifted to the higher wavenumber at $\sim 1370 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complex, indicating the bonding of the ligand to the metal through oxygen⁴. This fact is further supported by the disappearance of the broad ligand band $\sim 3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (OH) in the complex. The medium intensity ligand band at $\sim 1610 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C=N) shifted to lower

frequency ($\sim 1575 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complex, indicating the coordination of nitrogen of $>\text{C}=\text{NOH}$. The magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} complex (1.87 B.M.) is in accordance with one unpaired electron.

The electronic spectrum of the complex display two bands at 22 232 and 11 862 cm^{-1} similar to square-planar copper(II) complexes. The epr spectrum of the complex (recorded in polycrystalline state, diluted with zinc oxide) reveals a weak intensity signal at low field and intense signal at high field corresponding to g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} respectively. The values of g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and $\langle g \rangle$ are 2.128, 2.039 and 2.068 respectively. The $g_{\parallel} < 2.3$ reveals that M-L bonds are reasonably covalent. The spectrum shows square-planar environment around metal ion, except for a weak high field signal at g value ~ 1.95 .

The complex was found thermally stable upto 200° and starts decomposing after this temperature. It was completely decomposed at 362° giving CuO which was confirmed by comparing calculated and observed weight-loss.

Spectrophotometric measurements : The absorption spectra indicate that the absorbance of reagent is small at 449.8 nm where the complex has maximum absorbance. Hence the studies are carried out at 449.8 nm. The complex shows the maximum absorption in the pH range 6.0–11.0. Therefore subsequent studies were carried out at pH 8.0. The extraction is quantitative with $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ HMNQM, provided the aqueous phase volume does not exceed 80 ml and the amount of naphthalene-acetone solution is 3 ml (20%). The absorbance of the extract remains unchanged for upto 15 h. The extraction into microcrystalline naphthalene is very rapid and complete within 1 min.

Beer's law is obeyed upto 0.257–8.89 μg copper. The molar absorptivity was calculated to be $13675 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity $0.00464 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ copper at 449.8 nm. The interference of various anions and cations normally found associated with copper was studied. The amount of the diverse ion which brings about 2% variation in absorbance was taken as its tolerance limit. The results are given in Table 1. The study also shows that cyanide,

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF Cu

Amount of Cu taken = 2.54 ppm, pH = 8.0, λ_{\max} = 449.5 nm, Absorbance in absence of foreign ion = 0.547

Foreign ion	Added as	Amount added ppm	Absorbance	Absorbance deviation
Bromide	KBr	550	0.545	0.002
Chloride	NaCl	400	0.543	0.004
Fluoride	NaF	600	0.546	0.001
Nitrate	NaNO ₃	500	0.545	0.002
Nitrite	NaNO ₂	100	0.545	0.002
Phosphate	KH ₂ PO ₄	550	0.541	0.006
Tartrate	KNaC ₄ H ₇ O ₆	400	0.537	0.010
Oxalate	Na ₂ C ₂ O ₄	150	0.546	0.001
Thiosulphate	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	150	0.543	0.004
Citrate	Na ₃ C ₆ H ₅ O ₇	250	0.536	0.011
Thiocyanate	KCNS	200	0.542	0.005
Zn ^{II}	ZnSO ₄	80	0.541	0.006
Ca ^{II}	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	50	0.543	0.004
Cd ^{II}	Cd(NO ₃) ₂	60	0.544	0.003
Pd ^{II}	Pd(NO ₃) ₂	20	0.547	0.000
Mg ^{II}	MgSO ₄	10	0.547	0.000
Ba ^{II}	Ba(NO ₃) ₂	120	0.537	0.010
Os ^{VIII}	OsO ₄	2	0.535	0.012
(Thiocyanate masking agent)				
Pt ^{IV}	K ₂ PtCl ₆	4	0.545	0.002
Mn ^{II}	MnSO ₄	50	0.542	0.005
(F masking agent)				
Th ^{IV}	Th(NO ₃) ₄	40	0.541	0.006
(F masking agent)				
Mg ^{II}	MgSO ₄	5	0.547	0.000
U ^{VI}	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	20	0.545	0.002
Ag ^I	AgNO ₃	10	0.547	0.000
(F masking agent)				

Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Rh^{III} and Ru^{III} interfere seriously.

Determination of Cu in samples : Copper was determined in milk and steel samples following the proposed method and the results are presented in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

The present method is highly sensitive, selective, simple and rapid for trace analysis of metal ion as compared to the existing methods (Table 4).

Insecticidal study : Various sublethal concentration of naphthoquinone monoxime (HMNQM) were tested against *Aedes aegypti*, in the range 0–100 ppm. Larval mortality significantly increased at 40 ppm concentration of HMNQM. It was observed to be 57% at 100 ppm. Percent

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Cu IN MILK SAMPLES

Sample	Amount of Cu found (ppm)*	S.D.
Packed milk	0.279	0.0015
Buffalo's milk	0.257	0.0030

*Mean of five simultaneous determinations.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF Cu IN STEEL SAMPLES

Certified % composition of sample	% Cu taken	% Cu found*	%Error	S.D.
Sample-I :				
C, 0.24; Mn, 0.74;				
S, 0.25; Cu, 0.22;				
Si, 0.31; P, 0.021;				
Cr, 1.71; Mo, 0.021				
Sample-II :				
Si, 0.05; Zn, 0.075;				
Al, 7.50; Cu, 0.04;				
Mn, 0.24				

*Mean of five simultaneous determinations.

pupation was reduced markedly at 40 ppm and higher doses of HMNQM. This reduction was 40% at 50 ppm and 53.5% at 100 ppm with respect to control. Similarly, HMNQM affected adult formation that was 68% at 40 ppm, and got further reduced to 33.2% at 100 ppm. Larval and pupal period was delayed indicating the protection of metamorphic period of *Aedes* due to HMNQM treatment. This metamorphic period was significantly delayed at 20 ppm and onward doses of HMNQM, amounting to *ca.* 25% protraction. These characteristics observed under the influence of HMNQM, lead to reduction of growth index. For instance growth index was found to be decreased by 43.7, 55.6, 67.8 and 72.7% at 40, 50, 75 and 100 ppm respectively.

TABLE 4—SENSITIVITIES OF VARIOUS REAGENTS FOR COPPER USING SOLID PHASE EXTRACTION METHOD INTO MICROCRYSTALLINE NAPHTHALENE

Reagent	Sensitivity	Ref.
1. Acenaphthenequinonedioxime	0.068	5
2. Benzoin- α -oxime	0.024	6
3. 3-Bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methyl-acetophenoneoxime	0.095	7
4. 8-Hydroxyquinoline	0.012	8
5. 5,7-Dibromo-oxime	0.010	9
6. 5,7-Dichloro-oxime	0.010	10
7. 2-Methyl-8-hydroxyquinoline	0.012	11
8. Ammonium pyrrolidine-1-carbodithioate	0.009	12
9. Morpholine-4-carbodithioate	0.009	13
10. 3-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinonemonoxime	0.004	Present method

As reported by Kubo *et al.*¹⁴ about naturally occurring naphthoquinone plumbagin having ecdysis-inhibitor activity, and as apparent from the present study, 3-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone monoxime seems to be insecticidal. Regarding its less mammalian toxicity, its use in the water pockets having mosquito larvae could be considered.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade and used as received. Solvents were dried before use by conventional methods.

3-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone monoxime was prepared by the reported method¹⁵.

Synthesis of the complex : A mixture of ethanolic solutions of copper nitrate hexahydrate (1 mmol) and the ligand (2 mmol) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~2 h. The yellowish brown precipitate so formed was washed with water and ethanol successively and dried in vacuo over P₄O₁₀, (yield 65%) (Found : C, 56.28; H, 3.21; N, 5.66. CuC₂₂H₁₆N₂O₆ calcd. for : C, 56.41; H, 3.41; N, 5.98%). The purity was checked by tlc.

Potentiometric study : The potentiometric titrations were carried out at 25° in 0.1 M NaClO₄. The radiometer (PHM 83) was used to read the hydrogen ion concentration. The titrations were carried out in a covered double-walled glass cells in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen (N₂ purity ≈99%). All the calculations were done by fitting the calculated to the experimental potentiometric pH data using the programs PKAS¹⁶ and BEST¹⁷ with the aid of a PC/XT computer. Species distribution curves were drawn according to the program SPE¹⁷.

Elemental analyses were done on a Perkin-Elmer CHN analyser. The powder sample of the complex was heated at the heating rate of 10°/min on a Rigaku 8150 thermo-analyser. The magnetic susceptibility was measured by Faraday method using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant. The spectra were recorded as follows : Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Shimadzu spectrophotometer and X-band epr spectra on a JEOL-JES 3XG spectrometer at room temperature.

Spectrophotometric measurements : To an aliquot of sample solution (containing 2.54 µg of Cu) was added an ethanolic solution (1 ml) of 1 × 10⁻² M HMNQM, and its pH was adjusted to 7.0–8.5 with acetate buffer (2 ml) of pH 6 and 0.2 M NaOH. The volume was raised to 10 ml with double-distilled water. To this solution, 20% naphthalene-acetone solution (3 ml) was added and shaken for 1 min. The resulting solid was dissolved in DMF and dilute to 25 ml with DMF. The solution was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and its absorbance measured at 449.5 nm against a reagent blank.

Insecticidal activity : The third instar larvae of the mosquito *A. aegypti* were selected for the growth and developmental bioassay. Stock solution was prepared in acetone as 1000 ppm, and further 0–100 ppm concentrations were made in water. In each set of experiment third instar *Aedes* larvae in a batch of 25 each were treated with the desired concentration of naphthoquinone monoxime. Daily observation on mortality, survival and ecdysis were recorded. Developmental time, i.e. time taken by test larvae to undergo metamorphosis upto adult formation was noted and the growth index was computed. Mean values of different characteristics observed, were compared statistically by Duncan multiple range test.

References

1. P. W. BEANPRE and W. J. HOLLAND, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1984, **2**, 1; B. L. SHAH and C. M. DESAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 651; P. L. CHATTOPADHYA and S. K. MAJUMDAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, **25**, 504; R. B. SINGH, B. S. GARG and R. P. SINGH, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 425.
2. BASF A-G Ger. Pat. DE 3 545 904 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **107**, 198109); Sumistomo Chemical Co. Ltd., *Chem. Abstr.*, 1986, **104**, 83738; Pennval Corp., Jap. Pat. JP 61 176 559 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **106**, 66808).
3. M. O. MAXWELL and M. K. BRACHT, *Neurosci. Biobehav. Rev.*, 1991, **15**, 135 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1991, **115**, 107993).
4. B. KHERA, A. K. SHARMA and N. K. KAUSHIK, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 1177; *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1984, **1**, 172; *Acta Chem.*, 1984, **115**, 723; *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1984, **115**, 927.
5. J. L. LIN and M. SATAKE, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **32**, 105.
6. M. SHIMIZU, M. KATO and M. SATAKA, *Fukui Daigaku Kagakubu Kenkyu Hokoku*, 1976, **24**, 343.
7. S. MALHOTRA and K. LAL, *Orient J. Chem.*, 1985, **1**, 107.
8. M. S. KATO, M. SATAKE and NAGAOSA, *Fukui Daigaku Kagakubu Kenkyu Hokoku*, 1976, **24**, 349.
9. B. K. PURI, M. GAUTAM and T. FUJINAGA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1979, **52**, 3415.
10. M. SATAKE and Y. TANAKA, *Men. Fac. Eng. Fukui Univ.*, 1982, 3083.
11. M. SATAKE, T. SAKAKIBARA and M. SHIMIZU, *Men. Fac. Eng. Fukui Univ.*, 1975, **23**, 183.
12. T. FUJINAGA, Y. TAKAGI and M. SATAKE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1979, **52**, 2556.
13. M. GAUTAM, R. K. BANSAL and B. K. PURI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1981, **54**, 3178; C. L. SETHI, A. KUMAR, B. K. PURI and M. SATAKE, *Analyst*, 1983, **108**, 528; C. L. SETHI, A. KUMAR, M. SATAKE and B. K. PURI, *Talanta*, 1984, **31**, 848.
14. I. KUBO, M. VEHIDA and J. A. KLOCKS, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1983, **47**, 911.
15. R. K. SHARMA and S. K. SINDHWANI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1991, **103**, 607.
16. R. J. MOTEKAITIS and A. E. MARTELL, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1982, **60**, 2403.
17. R. J. MOTEKAITIS and A. E. MARTELL, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1982, **60**, 168.